

of this band upon the first, second and third ionisation potentials of the metals for mono-, bis- and tris-acetylacetonates, respectively. Lecomte¹ assigned a strong band $\sim 1400-1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu_{\sigma-\sigma}$. McGrady and Tobias¹³ have also studied the diorgano (alkyl and aryl)tinacetylacetonates. According to these workers, with the symmetrical ligands only two geometrical isomers, *cis* and *trans* are possible.

The most interesting characteristic of the ir spectrum of these complexes is that there is only one strong antisymmetric stretching vibration of the Sn—C band at 560 cm^{-1} while there is no-symmetric Sn—C stretching vibration. This will lead to conclude that the two biphenyl groups in these compounds are in the *trans*-position with the central tin atom. The four Sn—O bonds in these acetylacetonates, therefore, seems to be nearly equivalent.

The other absorption bands in these complexes can be assigned as follows. Most of these complexes show two strong bands in the $1500-1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The upper band $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to a perturbed C=O vibration and the lower band $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to a perturbed C=C stretching mode. The spectra in the $1500-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region are somewhat complicated. All the compounds show four absorption bands. Two bands at ~ 1475 and 1370 cm^{-1} and whose positions are same as in free acetylacetonate molecule, are assigned to CH_2 degenerate and symmetric deformation. Another two bands are $\sim 1390-1310$ and $1280-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and may be assigned to C—O stretching and C—C stretching, respectively. In the $1200-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, the C—H out-of-plane deformation band in diorganotinacetylacetonates appears at 820 and 755 cm^{-1} which is $20-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ higher than those in the usual metal-acetylacetonates. In the $700-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region there appear two slightly broad absorption located at ~ 695 and 570 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric Sn—O stretching vibrations, respectively.

¹H nmr spectra; The ¹H nmr spectra resonance signals due to biphenyl protons appear in the form of a doublet, a triplet and a doublet between $2-3\tau$. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{AcAc})_2$, resonance signal due to the methyl group of acetylacetonate appears as a singlet $\sim 8.0\tau$. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzAc})_2$, there is a multiplet in the region $2-3\tau$. It is due to the merging of the phenyl proton signals of benzoylacetonate into signals due to protons of biphenyl group. There is a singlet $\sim 7.9\tau$ due to the protons of the methyl group of the benzoylacetonate. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzbz})_2$, a multiplet in the region $2-3\tau$ is again due to the mixing of the phenyl protons in the biphenyl signals. In all these complexes, there is a signal $\sim 4\tau$ due to CH protons.

In case of $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{AcAc})_2$ and $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzAc})_2$, there is only a single singlet $\sim 8.0\tau$ due to methyl protons which

suggests that these complexes are having *trans*-configuration and the biphenyl groups are probably rotating freely¹³. If there would have been *cis*-configuration in these complexes, we should get a doublet for methyl protons as there is only a two-fold axis with the molecule having two sets of two symmetrically equivalent R' groups, whereas in *trans*-configuration all ligand biphenyl groups form a symmetrical equivalent set. Thus, on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies all the complexes have biphenyl groups in *trans*-position and have coordination number six, β -diketone moiety acting as bidentate ligand.

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Metal Complexes as Ligands. Polynuclear Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes with Copper(II)- and Nickel(II)-Salicylaldimines

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Manuscript received 13 September 1984, revised 6 May 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

IN continuation of our previous work¹, the present study involves the synthesis and characterisation of the complexes formed by Ni²⁺- and Cu²⁺-salicylaldimines with alkaline earth salts of inorganic and organic acids.

Experimental

To a mixture of CuES or NiES in chloroform and absolute ethanol (1:1), was added alkaline

NOTES

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Alkaline earth metal	$\nu_{C=O}$	μ_{eff} at 30° B.M.
			N	C	Cu/Ni			
CuES	Green	322					1532	1.90
CuES.Mg(8HQ) ₂	Light green	375	8.53 (8.72)	—	9.90 (9.98)	3.59 (3.74)	1530	—
CuES.CaCl ₂	Violet	286	6.03 (6.35)	42.82 (43.5)	14.30 (14.40)	8.89 (8.08)	1540	1.95
CuES.CaI ₂	Violet	285	4.39 (4.49)	35.0 (36.8)	11.82 (11.83)	—	1543	—
CuES.SrCl ₂	Violet	270	5.56 (5.53)	38.48 (39.4)	13.02 (13.00)	—	1541	1.91
CuES.BaCl ₂	Green	298	5.00 (5.20)	34.5 (35.8)	11.50 (11.61)	—	1548	1.91
CuES.BaBr ₂	Violet	305	4.39 (4.46)	26.5 (27.4)	10.00 (10.11)	—	1523	1.99
NiES	Bright red	330					1536	
NiES.Mg(ONP) ₂	Red*	230	8.54 (8.93)	—	9.00 (8.93)	3.58 (3.83)	1536	Dia.
NiES.Mg(8HQ) ₂	Yellow	282	8.85 (8.89)	—	9.06 (9.21)	3.68 (3.78)	1537	0.919
NiES.MgCl ₂	Red*	295	6.57 (6.67)	—	13.88 (13.98)	5.57 (5.71)	1537	Dia.
NiES.MgBr ₂	Orange	287	5.47 (5.50)	—	11.00 (11.53)	4.59 (4.71)	1542	1.061
NiES.MgI ₂	Orange	290	4.56 (4.62)	—	9.57 (9.73)	3.89 (3.98)	1544	Dia.
NiES.CaCl ₂	Orange	320	6.39 (6.42)	44.92 (44.2)	13.38 (13.47)	8.89 (9.10)	1545	Dia.
NiES.CaI ₂	Orange	298	4.85 (4.54)	29.1 (30.9)	9.42 (9.48)	—	1546	Dia.
NiES.SrCl ₂	Orange	280	5.52 (5.79)	38.4 (39.7)	12.01 (12.14)	—	1542	Dia.
NiES.BaCl ₂	Orange	280	5.00 (5.25)	35.6 (36.1)	11.00 (11.81)	—	1543	Dia.

*Crystalline.

earth metal salts (2:1). The mixture was refluxed and subsequently the precipitate formed in hot condition was filtered, washed with a mixture of absolute ethanol and chloroform (1:1) and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are insoluble in non-aqueous solvents and are stable under dry condition. The colour, decomposition temperature and analytical data of these complexes are given in Table 1.

The ir bands of binuclear alkaline earth metal complexes are given in Table 1. The C—O (1530 cm⁻¹) band consistently shifted up by 16-30 cm⁻¹. The same type of shifting was observed in case of transition and alkali metal complexes¹, due to delocalisation of electrons towards the benzene ring², and the phenolic C—O link attaining considerable amount of partial double bond character (C=O). The above assignments were also found compatible with those made for the C=O links in metal acetylacetonates³ and bis(*N*-methylsalicylaldimino)zinc(II)⁴.

The binuclear copper-alkaline earth metal complexes have magnetic moment values in the range of

1.90-1.95 B.M., suggesting the same geometry of CuES (1.90 B.M.) in the alkaline earth metal adducts. NiES is diamagnetic; their binuclear complexes are also diamagnetic, except NiES.MgBr₂ (1.06 B.M.) and NiES.Mg(8HQ)₂ (0.92 B.M.), suggesting the same geometry of NiES in adducts. The slight deviation from strict diamagnetism in the case of the above two, is generally indicative of one of the types of so called 'anomalous behaviour'. Thus it is suggested that coordination number of Ni of NiES has not been raised.

There being not much difference in the electronic spectra of distorted octahedral, tetrahedral and square planar Cu²⁺, a detailed interpretation of its electronic spectra has not been made. The absorption band of medium intensity in NiES at 450 nm and of binuclear alkaline earth metal complexes at 400-500 nm, suggest the same square planar geometry. As the coordination number of Ni²⁺ in NiES remains the same in the adducts, it is apparent that the alkaline earth metal salts are not attached through Ni²⁺ ion. No other absorption bands have been observed in the range of 600-1200 nm in the binuclear adducts.

Hence, oxygen bridged polynuclear structure has been suggested for these complexes, bonding

being through phenolic oxygen atoms of transition metal complexes and alkaline earth metal.

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Complexes of Sulphaguanidine with Copper and Silver

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Manuscript received 16 May 1984, revised 1 July 1985,
accepted 29 October 1985

IN continuation of our work on sulphonamides¹⁻³ we describe herein complexes of sulphaguanidine with cupric chloride and silver nitrate, keeping this in view that some metal complexes are found to be more potent than their parent sulphonamides. Kaushal and coworkers⁴⁻⁵ have prepared a large number of metal sulphonamide complexes.

Experimental

Composition of the complexes: Standard solution of cupric chloride (0.02 M), silver nitrate (0.02 M) and sulphaguanidine (0.01 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure ethanol. The ligand solution (10 ml) was diluted to 50 ml and titrated against the metal salt solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and dip type of electrodes at 28°. The results after volume corrections indicate 2 : 1 sulphaguanidine cupric chloride complex and 1 : 1 sulphaguanidine silver nitrate complex, respectively.

Sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride complex: Sulphaguanidine (1.0 g) and cupric chloride (0.4 g) in 2 : 1 molar proportion were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A dark green solution was obtained which on refluxing over

water-bath for 30 min gave a green complex. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried (1.1 g), m.p. 185°.

Sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complex: Sulphaguanidine (1 g) and silver nitrate (0.8 g) in 1 : 1 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A white crystalline complex was obtained, which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried (1.4 g), m.p. 191°.

Analytical results of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. Nitrogen was estimated by modified Kjeldahl's method⁶, sulphur by Messenger's method and metals by standard volumetric or gravimetric procedures.

Particle size of the complexes and sulphaguanidine was determined by the microscope having eye piece 10 × objective 10 : 1/0.30 and stage micrometer 0.01 mm (Erma, Japan). Particle size was 75-165 for sulphaguanidine with white needle shaped crystals, and 8-15, and 15-30 for sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride and sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complexes, respectively with green spherical crystals and white rectangular crystals.

Bacteriostatic studies were done by disc method on *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus proteus*, *Bacillus pyocyaneus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi A* pathogens.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titrations indicate that sulphaguanidine forms 2 : 1 complex with copper, and 1 : 1 complex with silver. Yamabe and coworkers⁷ have reported 2 : 1 ratio for various copper sulpha drug complexes. Turner and coworkers⁸ have suggested 1 : 1 complex of sulphadiazene with silver. Narang and Gupta⁹ have reported 1 : 1 complex of sulphapyridine with silver nitrate.

The present studies are supported by the work of Tskitishvili *et al.*¹⁰ on sulphapyradizine complexes with Cu, Zn, Cd *etc.* In these complexes donation of lone pair of electrons is shown by oxygen of SO₂ group and nitrogen of substituted group of sulphonamide. Sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride and sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complexes on boiling with water gives test for chloride and nitrate ions which confirms that these ions

TABLE I

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Metal	Cl/NO ₃	C	H	N	S
(C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S) ₂ CuCl ₂	11.21 (11.29)	12.16 (12.57)	29.90 (29.89)	3.31 (3.58)	19.85 (19.92)	11.57 (11.40)
(C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S)AgNO ₃	27.98 (28.10)	-	22.70 (21.90)	2.94 (2.62)	14.29 (14.59)	08.18 (08.35)